

A novel method for the synthesis of allylic sulfides from disulfides and allylytterbium bromide

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In presence of trace of methyl iodide (MeI), allylytterbium bromide is formed by the reaction of metallic ytterbium and allylic bromide, which reacts with disulfides to give the corresponding allylic sulfides in good yields under mild and neutral conditions.

Allylic sulfides are a class of useful synthetic intermediates, and many synthetic methods have been reported for preparation of allylic sulfides, for example, the alkylation of thiols¹, the reaction of alkyl halide with sodium sulfide, addition of thiophenol with alkene², reduction of disulfides with copper in the presence of halide, reduction of sulphoxides with titanium(II) chloride, deoxygenation of sulfoxides with triphenylphosphine/iodine/sodium iodide³, synthesis of allylthioethers via allyldialkyltelluronium salts. Our group has studied synthesis of allylic sulfides by reaction of disulfides with allylsamarium bromide⁴. Here, we report the reaction of allylytterbium bromide with disulfides to afford allylic sulfides in good yields (Scheme 1). The advantages of this method are rapid reaction and simple operation.

Results and Discussion

In our experimental work, it was found that ytterbium metal neither reacts directly with allyl bromide to form allylytterbium bromide as does samarium, nor can be activated by addition of KI or NaI and I₂ as can samarium. But surprisingly, in the presence of a catalytic amount of MeI or CH₂I₂, ytterbium can react with allyl bromide to form allylytterbium bromide easily (Table 1).

Table 1. Preparation of allylmetal bromide and reaction condition

Metal	Activating reagent	Reaction condition		Product
		Time	Temp.	
Sm	-	3 h	25	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ SmBr
Yb	-	3 h	25	-
Yb	-	3 h	0	-
Sm	I ₂	1 h	25	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ SmBr
Yb	I ₂	1 h	25	-
Yb	I ₂	1 h	0	-
Sm	KI	1 h	25	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ SmBr
Yb	KI	1 h	25	-
Yb	KI	1 h	0	-
Yb	KI	15 min	25	-
Yb	KI	15 min	10	-
Yb	KI	15 min	0	-
Yb	MeI	15 min	0	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ YbBr
Yb	CH ₂ I ₂	15 min	0	CH ₂ =CHCH ₂ YbBr

It was also found that disulfides react with allylytterbium bromide more easily than with allylsamarium bromide (Table 2). It was shown that both dialkyl disulfides and diaryl disulfides can react with allylytterbium bromide to give allylsulfides in moderate to good yields. Dialkyl disulfides (such as dihexyldisulfide) give allylsulfides in moderate yields. Diaryl disulfides give the corresponding arylsulfides in good yields.

It is noteworthy that electrostatic effect in the aromatic ring affects the yields of allylsulfides. If the substituted groups are electron-withdrawing, the yields are higher than those of electron-donating groups.

Table 2 also shows that allylytterbium bromide is more active than allylsamarium bromide.

Table 2. Reaction conditions and yields of allylic disulfides (2a-i)

Compd. no.	R	Metal	Time h	Temp. °C	Yield* %
2a	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	Sm	2	Reflux	66
		Yb	2	25	65
b	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇	Sm	2	Reflux	70
		Yb	2	25	72
c	<i>n</i> -C ₁₀ H ₂₁	Sm	2	Reflux	72
		Yb	2	25	73
d	<i>n</i> -C ₁₆ H ₃₃	Sm	2	Reflux	75
		Yb	1	25	77
e	C ₆ H ₅	Sm	1	Reflux	84
		Yb	1	25	85
f	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	Sm	1	Reflux	80
		Yb	1	25	79
g	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Sm	1	Reflux	81
		Yb	1	25	82
h	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	Sm	1	Reflux	86
		Yb	1	25	88
i	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	Sm	1	Reflux	82
		Yb	1	25	83

*Yields of isolated products based on disulfides.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was distilled from sodium-benzophenone ketyl immediately prior to use. All reactions were conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker AC-80 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard and IR spectra on an IR-408 spectrometer.

Allylation of disulfides with allylytterbium bromide.

General procedure: Ytterbium powder (173 mg, 1 mmol) and one drop of methyl iodide were mixed at room temperature under a nitrogen atmosphere. The metal was then warmed slightly to be activated for about 15 min, then cooled to 0°. Allyl bromide (136 mg, 1.2 mmol) in THF (10 ml) was introduced by a syringe. The mixture was stirred at 0° for 10–15 min. A brown solution of allylytterbium bromide was formed.

A solution of disulfides (0.5 mmol) in THF (2 ml) was added to the brown solution of allylytterbium bromide by a syringe in one portion at 25° under nitrogen atmosphere. After being stirred for given period of time (Table 2). The reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction was quenched with HCl (0.1 mol dm⁻³; 5 ml) and extracted with ether (2 × 30 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with brine (2 × 20 ml), dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, concen-

trated in vacuum and purified by preparative TLC on silica gel (cyclohexane as eluent) to give allyl sulfides.

Allylation of disulfides with allylsamarium bromide.

General procedure: The allylation of disulfides with allylsamarium bromide was performed according to the reported procedure⁴: **2a**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 2975, 2880, 1660, 1490, 1400, 920, 730 cm⁻¹, δ 0.95–1.68 (1H, m, alkyl-H), 3.00–3.45 (4H, m, allyl-CH₂, =CH₂), 4.94 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, SCH₂), 5.45–6.00 (1H, m, CH=); **2b**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 2975, 2880, 1650, 1465, 1400, 925, 720 cm⁻¹, δ 0.98–1.76 (15H, m), 3.10–3.55 (4H, m, allyl-CH₂, =CH₂), 4.95 (2H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, SCH₂), 5.45–6.05 (1H, m, CH=); **2c**, oil, ν_{\max} 2970, 2882, 1645, 1460, 1395, 923, 725 cm⁻¹, δ 0.96–1.75 (19H, m), 3.10–3.56 (4H, m, allyl-CH₂, =CH₂), 4.94 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, SCH₂), 5.47–6.00 (1H, m, CH=); **2d**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 2965, 2880, 1650, 1465, 1390, 922, 728 cm⁻¹, δ 0.95–1.75 (31H, m, alkyl-H), 3.10–3.58 (4H, m, allyl-CH₂, =CH₂), 4.99 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, SCH₂), 5.45–6.05 (1H, m, CH=); **2e**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 3100, 2950, 1650, 1600, 1490, 1095, 920, 740, 695 cm⁻¹, δ 3.48 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, =CH₂), 5.05 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, SCH₂), 5.45–6.15 (1H, m, CH=), 7.00–7.50 (5H, m, ArH); **2f**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 3080, 2965, 1650, 1520, 1480, 1085, 770, 700 cm⁻¹, δ 2.90 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, =CH₂), 3.45 (2H, s), 4.90 (2H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, SCH₂), 5.40–6.05 (1H, m, CH=), 7.00–7.35 (5H, m, ArH); **2g**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 3100, 2970, 1650, 1520, 1400, 990, 920, 830 cm⁻¹, δ 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.40 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, =CH₂), 5.03 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, SCH₂), 5.46–6.10 (1H, m, CH=), 6.98–7.30 (5H, m, ArH); **2h**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 3110, 2955, 1650, 1480, 1095, 930, 695 cm⁻¹, δ 3.43 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, =CH₂), 4.85 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, SCH₂), 5.55–5.95 (1H, m, CH=), 6.95–7.60 (4H, m, ArH); **2i**, oil⁴, ν_{\max} 3090, 2980, 1650, 1515, 1480, 1090, 920, 770, 700 cm⁻¹, δ 3.40 (2H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, =CH₂), 3.50 (2H, s), 5.0 (2H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, SCH₂), 5.50–6.15 (1H, m, CH=), 7.00–7.50 (5H, m, ArH).

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